

1 **ERBB2 loss and ERBB4 gain functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm**
2 **lineage specification.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for ERBB2 loss concomitant with ERBB4 induction in germ layer lineage choice
11 from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*.

12 Citations

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15 modulates neuroblast migration and placement in the adult forebrain. *Nature neuroscience*, 7(12),
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